

A Study on E-Commerce and Its Market Competition among Competitors in Palayamkottai Area

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Abstract

Electronic commerce is the process of doing business through the internet and other computer networks. All the facilities are available on the internet to buy or sell the products. E-Commerce covers outward-facing processes that touch customers, suppliers and external partners, including sales, marketing, order taking, and delivery, customer service, purchasing of raw materials.

E-Commerce has made the shopping easier for people by reducing the physical work and save time. The consumer user the networks for home shopping and home banking. The people come to know about the advertisement on the internet. E-Commerce helps to increase the speed of service delivery. It's also have more market competition. E-Commerce gives a large amount of profit but there many competitions between the sellers.

So the researcher made the study in the palayamkottai area about the level of competition and also how competition made effects in their sales. The study was made with 60 respondents in palayamkottai area.

Keyword: customer service, marketing, competition, buyer and seller.

Introduction

Electronic commerce is the business environment in which information for the buying, selling and transportation of goods and service moves electronically. It also involves an exchange of goods. But the exchange of goods is conducted online. A lot of companies are conducting transactions over the web. E-commerce applications can be witnessed in banking; ticketing includes airlines, bus, railways, bill payments, hotel booking, retailing digital downloads, education, entertainment, infotainment, finance, etc. Internet users in India used the internet to buy travel tickets and to carry out online shopping especially products like books, flowers, gifts, etc. Few people also deal in stocks and shares through the internet, known as online trading. The report pointed out the percentages of the key activities carried out by internet users in 1. E-mail, 2. Chatting, 3. Information, 4. Entertainment, 5. E-commerce. Perfect competition is a type of market where there is a large number of buyers and sellers; the sellers sell the identical or homogeneous product. There is also free entry and exists of the firms. Both of the buyers and sellers have perfect knowledge of the market.

Market Competition There Are 3 Types

1. Direct competitors –similar products and revenue goal
2. Indirect competitors. – Similar products different revenue goal
3. Replacement competitors. – substitute products same customer time /money.

Objectives of The Study

1. To study e-commerce and its market competition analysis of the competitors.
2. To know the reasons for purchasing a particular product.
3. To identify the quality of the product compare to competitors.

Methodology

This project is based on information collected from primary sources as well as secondary data. After the detailed study, an attempt has been made to study e-commerce and its market competition in the competitors to the product and services. In collecting requisite data and information regarding the topic selected.

Analysis

Table 1 The Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Numbers	Percentage
Age (years)	21-30	25	42
	31-40	15	25
	Above 41	20	33
	Total	60	100
Gender	Male	35	58
	Female	25	42
	Total	60	100
Experience (years)	1-10 years	16	27
	11-20 years	15	25
	Above 20 years	29	48
	Total	60	100
Marital status	Married	36	60
	Unmarried	24	40
	Total	60	100
Income	Below 10000	16	27
	10001-20000	15	25
	20001-30000	17	28
	Above 30001	12	20
	Total	60	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table explains that 42%of the respondents are in the age group of 21-30 years.25%of The resp ondents are in the age group of 31-40 years. 33%of the respondents are in the age group of above 41 years.58% of the respondents are male.42% of the respondents are female.27% of the respondents are 1-10 years experience. 25% of the respondents are 11-20years experience.48% Of the respondents are above 20years.60%of the respondents are married.40% of the respondents

are unmarried. 27% of the respondents have the income below 10000.25% of the respondents have the income 10001-20000. 28% of the respondents have the income 20001-30000. 20% of the respondents have the income above 30001.

Table 2 The Special Training for E-Commerce

S.No	Training	Respondent	Percentage
1	Yes	34	57
2	No	26	43
	Total	60	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table explains that 57% of the respondents using for the special training.26% of the respondents are not using training.

Table 3 Level of Market Competition

S.no	Level	Respondent	Percentage
1	High level	29	48
2	Low level	15	25
3	Middle level	16	27
	Total	30	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table explains that 48% of the respondents are high-level market competition.25%of The respondents are low-level market competition.27% of the respondents are middle-level market competition.

Table 4 Types of the Product

S.No	Product	Respondent	Percentage
1	Consumable Goods	25	42
2	Electronic goods	15	25
3	Home appliances	20	33
	Total	60	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table explains that 42% of the respondents are consumable goods.25% of the respondents are electronic goods.33% of the respondents are home appliances.

Table 5 Lack of Competition for Competitors

S.No	Level	Respondent	Percentage
1	Response time	12	20
2	knowledge	17	28
3	Ability to listen	15	25
4	Understanding about consumers	16	27
	Total	60	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table explains that 20% of the respondents are response time.28% of the respondents are knowledge.25% of the respondents are the ability to listen.27% of the respondents understand about consumers.

Table 6 Customer Service

S.no	Service	Respondent	Percentage
1	Website contact form	20	33
2	E-mail	15	25
3	Telephone	25	42
	Total	60	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table explains that 33% of the respondents are web site contact.25% of the respondents are e-mail.42% of the respondents are services.

Findings

- 42%of the respondents are in the age group of 21-30 years.
- 58% of the respondents are male.
- 48% of the respondents are above 20years.
- 60%of the respondents are married.
- 28% of the respondents have the income 20001-30000.
- 57% of the respondents using for the special training
- 48% of the respondents are high-level market competition.
- 42% of the respondents are consumable goods.
- 28% of the respondents are knowledge.
- 42% of the respondents are services.

Suggestion

Competitors will consistently try to offer better customer service, product quality and marketing. In the healthy market, buyers will demand the best solutions for their specific needs. Competitors most firms get lost in the day to day of maintaining their business. People are like to the e-commerce and its market competition to the competitors. Customer services by being more responsive to their needs and expectation.

Conclusion

The main conclusion was that the overall level of know-how and knowledge among Finnish web stores is too low. Additionally, the best method of achieving competitive advantage is through strategic differentiation, which then again is best reached through the brand, service and product offering based positioning – all made more effective by localization. Several recommendations for the web stores as well as other parties are made in the thesis.

References

- Albert H, Judd, Rivers. (2006) “creating a winning E-business.” Wagner course Technology Thomas is learning pp 37-255.
- Kolakata, R., & Robinson, M. (1999), E-Business Roadmap for success Addison- Wesley 112-149.
- Munindar, P., & Singh, (2001). An Evolutionary look at e-commerce, IEEE internet computing vol 5, No: 2, pp 6-7
- Raj Veeramani., & Nancy Talbert. (1999). where Aro uses in global e-commerce. IT professional, Vol.1. No: 6 pp 46-52
- Sawy. (2001). Redesigning Enterprise process for E-business Mcorow Hill, pp 29-40.

Web Sources

http://epub.lib.aalto.fi/en/ethesis/pdf/12849/hse_ethesis_12849.pdf

<https://accountlearning.com/14-differences-between-e-commerce-and-traditional-commerce/>

<https://www.bartleby.com/essay/Study-of-Consumer-Preference-Towards-Cadbury-and-PKFEW2LK6YYS>

<https://www.entrepreneurmag.co.za/advice/growing-a-business/compete-to-win/10-ways-competition-can-improve-your-business/>

<https://www.ukessays.com/essays/economics/introduction-to-the-perfect-competition-economics-essay.php>